

A Study on the Benefits of Social Media Website for Modern Recruitment Process

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Abstract

Social media recruitment is a way of using the social media sites such as facebook, linkedin, to advertise jobs, find talent and communicate with potential recruits about company culture. The aim of this study is to analyze the importance of social media websites for recruitment purposes, with this aim the researcher as selected 50 respondents randomly to do questionnaires survey. The objective of this paper is to find out the satisfaction and the problem faced by the applicant in the social media websites for the recruitment. The methodology used for collecting data is through primary source. The main findings of this research paper are to analyze the satisfaction level and benefits of social media websites.

Introduction

In modern society the role of internet plays a important part and opens many opportunity for companies to communicate. Now days most of the companies are opting social networking sites for recruitment process. Social recruitment is concerned with sourcing candidate for jobs via social media channel and social media network. The purpose of social media recruitment is to reach wide no of people across the world and also helps the candidate to get the information about the requirement of job in the companies.

The various social media sites which are chosen to advertise about the job requirement in companies are Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter. Social media sites help to increase job visibility for the job seekers. It creates better employee brand awareness in social sites and also reduces cost of hire for the companies. It is the most time consuming method for recruitment. According to 2018 career builder survey, 70 percent of employers use social media to screen candidates during the hiring process and about 43 percent of employers use social media to check on current employees. Recruiting with social networking sites is fast becoming a way of life, since the beginning of the social media era. Our world revolves around posts or tweets and communication has become extremely convenient, quick and effective.

Review of Literature

Saud Salem bamokarh (2017) conducted a research on the role of social media in recruitment. The research paper aimed on critical analysis on role of social media in the recruitment of student. The main purpose of the paper was to investigate the effect of social media in the recruitment process of the business organization and its impact on the student as well. The methodology used in the research was sampling method, sampling size and result of pylon study was included. The researcher has used anthology philosophy as variable of study. The researcher as concluded that 48% of student used Facebook and YouTube are social media recruitment site.

HumeraSiddigi and AftabAlam (2016) conducted a research on social media and recruitment. The social media in recruitment provided an platform for individuals and organization to connect together and also help them to recruit employee through use of social networking sites. The research aims was to focus on new ways of recruiting and its effectiveness on management. The paper was descriptive study and primary information collect through structured questionnaires. The data analysis is based on correlation and regression analysis. The finding reviles the relationship between recruitment and social media is positive with moderate degree.

Fawzieh Mohammed Masid Assistant Professor (2015) conducted a research on deployment of social media in the recruitment process. The purpose of this paper was to assess how employers can construct best use of social media as a part of recruitment process. This paper is focused on recognized difference between social media websites and their impact. The research model was in direct and strong relationship between qualities of social networking sites and effective recruitment. To test the hypothesis the construct and variable method was used in research. The data analysis is based on correlation matrix and component matrix. The author concluded to expand the knowledge about social networking sites in recruitment.

Vaishlilal and Shruthi Aggarwal (2013) conducted a study on analyzing the effect of social media on recruitment. The purpose of study was to know the use of internet recruitment. Which has become popular both among the employer as well the job seeker. The study aimed at testing the popularity and effectiveness of social media sites and also finding out the reliability and trust worthiness of sites. The research methodology was descriptive in nature based on primary and secondary data. The data analysis is based on correlation, T-test and percentage. They concluded that the majority of respondents are aware of social networking sites.

W .Schoenmaker’s and R.Wesselinkconducted a research on the role of social media in recruitment and selection process. The research was on growing availability of high speed internet access added the popularity of the concept of social media which led to the creation of social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter. The growth in social media has impact on the use of social media within HR practices, especially in the recruitment and selection process. The research method was conducted by a literature review, the literature review is structured according to the framework of promises and pitfalls lead to answer the main question of this thesis. The study showed HR professionals use SNSs frequently in the U.S during the recruitment and selection process.

Objectives

- To know whether the social media are better than traditional method for the recruitment process.
- To study on the accessibility and usage of social media website.
- To know the benefits of social media recruitment for recruiter as well as job seekers.
- To find out the satisfaction level of social media websites.
- To find out the problems faced by social media websites.

Research Methodology

The research is based on both primary and secondary data. The secondary data collected through Internet, Journals, books and other published research papers, internet helped us with websites that related to the topic of research. The primary data collected through structured questionnaires in electronic form which was distributed through wed. 50 questions were constructed and collected through electronic form, the response rate was 100%. Both dependent and independent variable were measured on a five-point liker scale with range from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. Other than the measurement of variables the demographic section was also included in the questionnaire which was composed of gender, level of education and social media site they mostly use.

Chart 1 Access of Social Media for Recruitment

The chart 1 depicts that about 80% of the respondent accepted that they use social media for the recruitment and only 20% of the respondent were not using the social media site for recruitment.

Chart 2 Most Accessed Social Media Website

Chart 2 depicts that most of the people use facebook and linked in as 42% of respondent use facebook and 42% use linkedin. On the other hand 8% use twitter, 13% use instagram, 1% use naukri, 1% use google, 1% had never used any of the above the social media website.

Chart 3 Compare of Social Media Site than Traditional Methods

Chart 3 depicts that 42% of respondent agreed that social media site are more comfortable than traditional method, 44% of respondent were neutral, 6% of respondent strongly agreed and remaining 6% of respondent disagreed.

Chart 4 Is Social Media is Time Consuming

Chart 4 depicts that about 44% of respondent had chosen neutral that they feel social media is time consuming for recruitment 28% of respondent agreed, 18% of respondent disagreed and 8% of respondent strongly disagreed.

Chart 5 Satisfaction of Social Media Recruitment

Chart 5 depicts that about 58% of respondent were chosen neutral about the satisfaction of social media for recruitment, 36% of respondent were agreed and 6% of respondent disagreed that social media is not satisfied.

Chart 6 Often usage of Social Media Website

Chart 6 depicts about often usage of social media site for recruitment purpose 44% respondent use the social media site more often 30% of respondent uses once in a week and remaining 26% of respondent uses once in a month.

Chart 7 Problem faced in Social Media Site for Recruitment

Chart 7 depicts about the problem faced by the respondent 53% of responded faced the problem of lack of clarity of job at the time of accessing the social media site. 27.9% respondent faced genuinity of the job , 14% of the respondent faced lack of proper communication about the job and remaining 3% of responded said that they didn't face any problems

Chart 8 Responses from the Recruiters

Chart 8 depicts about the responses from the recruiters to the respondent 60% of the respondent agreed that they get the responses from the respondent and 40% of the respondent said that they don't get any responses from the recruiters

Benefits for Recruiter using Social Media in Recruitment

1. The higher quality candidates sourced through social media networks for several potential reasons. People actively engaged in social media tend to be more knowledgeable about business trends.
2. Sourcing candidates via social media sites is less expensive and lower costs than traditional search methods.
3. Social media recruiting techniques can shorten the time-to-hire, recruiter can communicate with potential talent better and candidates can response immediately.
4. Social media helps to showcasing the company’s culture and values, so as to attract more number of candidates for better job.

Benefits for Candidate using Social Media in Recruitment

- Easily accessible to the vacancy of post in an companies and know more detail about the post in an companies.
- It saves time as well as transportation cost incurred by the candidates.
- Through social media the candidate can access different job roles at their finger tip and get more information about the job
- The candidates can choose their right job among the various alternatives given by many companies.
- The social media helps the candidate to come across various applications such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Naukri etc...

Findings

1. With regard to the use of social media recruitment it is found most of the respondent accept that social media is better than traditional method.
2. This research found that the use of Facebook and LinkedIn is much higher among the other social media sites like Twitter, Instagram and Naukri.
3. The respondent accepts that the social media recruitment is most beneficiary for the recruitment purpose.
4. The problem which is faced by the job seekers is the clarity about the job, genuinity of the job and lack of communication.

Suggestions

- The recruiter can provide proper Clarity and description about the job in the social Media websites, so that the candidates will have clear about the job.
- Most of the fresher are not aware of social media websites, the recruiter can reach Out and provide a awareness for the fresher’s in colleges.

Conclusion

The key objective of the researcher is to know the benefits, satisfaction and problem faced by the candidate in the social media websites. Social media websites in recruitment plays a major role in the modern era. The accessibility of the social media websites are easily reached to the candidates as usage of social media websites are increasing day by day. Therefore it is more comfortable for both recruiters as well as candidates.

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